

Business, Management and Economics Research

ISSN(e): 2412-1770, ISSN(p): 2413-855X

Vol. 2, No. 4, pp: 74-80, 2016

URL: <http://arpgweb.com/?ic=journal&journal=8&info=aims>

Employee Potentiality vs. Job Responsibility: Employers' View

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Abstract: Learning and expression of the fact-and-reality cannot take place at instance coincidentally. The variations embodied into both assessing and justification of traits and quality of an incumbent set up parameters based on some skills or factors. This study focused on the key factors having influence in selecting an employee for an organization. Due to varied nature of selection methods and variability, the factors were found disperse behavior in different dimensions. The researcher craved to identify the impact of scattered factors in selection of an employee and made some clusters through similarities and variability by Varimax Rotation Factor Analysis. From several factors, this study found that maximum preference toned with leadership skill under which leadership, oral communication, presentation skill, decision making capacity, capability to work in group, knowledge about corporate world, written communication, analytical ability, innovativeness, fellow feeling, and dedication to work were worth considerable. The study also encompassed other influential factors namely, team spirit, belongingness skills, analytical ability, change management skill, and human skills.

Keywords: Selection factors; Job responsibility; Leadership skill; Entry level job.

1. Introduction

Organizations devote substantial resources to establish strong measures to maintain a 'good fit' for job (Caldwell. *et al.*, 1990). Sometimes a careful review of each candidate's educational background and work history will help the employers to select better workers, and sometimes using additional tests will be beneficial (USDLETA (U.S. Department of Labor Employment and Training Administration), 2000). According to traditional views, selection of human resources measures job related characteristics , such as, past experience, intelligence, knowledge, skills and abilities, and greater selectivity leads to such desirable outcomes as high performance and satisfaction , though there are arguments against non-job related criteria for selection process as attractiveness (Dipboye *et al.*, 1977) and goal orientation and interpersonal skills (Rynes and Barry, 1990) whereas socially based criteria as personal chemistry, values, personality traits, possibly, on how closely recruits preferences match organizational values.

To achieve an active workforce, employers must proactively identify and eliminate barriers in recruitment and selection practices that tend to limit opportunities for groups and individuals for reasons unrelated to merit. Those barriers are typically identified through workforce analysis, which is useful for identifying employment anomalies which merit further review. While the numbers may indicate or even uncover a barrier, they should never play a role in ultimate employment decisions. Rather, they should prompt action to eradicate the practice or procedure to ensure equal and fair opportunities. Organizations must follow a "selection justification memorandum" citing the rationale for the selection and also based on the merit and summarizes job related reasons. The selection memorandum should cite evidence of the selectees, like technical knowledge, experience, management or leadership experience, as appropriate, and other job-related reasons justifying the selection (Department of Veterans Affairs (DVA), 2010).

In selecting employees, employers can conveniently classify test according to whether they measure cognitive (mental) abilities, motor and physical abilities, personality and interests, or achievements (Siegel and Lane, 1982). Again, industrial psychologists often emphasize the 'big five' personality dimensions as they apply to personnel testing: extraversion, emotional stability/neuroticism, agreeableness, consciousness, and openness to experience (Cellar, 1996). To use assessment tools properly, employers must be aware of the inherent limitations of any assessment procedures and the legal issues involved in assessment and can track tools by whole-person approach, unbiased and fair jud (USDLETA (U.S. Department of Labor Employment and Training Administration), 2000).

2. Objectives

The study has been covered the following key objectives, as such:

- (i) To expose the key factors to be considered in selecting an employee for an organization.

- (ii) To rank the factors influencing the selection process at entry level job from opinions of sample respondents.

3. Literature Review

Selection procedures refer to any procedure singly or in combination to make a personal decision making, but not limited to, paper-and-pencil tests, computer-administered tests, performance tests, work samples, inventories, projective techniques, polygraph examinations, individual assessments, assessment center evaluations, biographical data forms or scored application blank, interviews, educational requirements, experience requirements, reference checks, background investigations, physical requirements, physical ability tests appraisals of job performance computer-based test interpretations, and estimates of advancement potential. These selection procedures include methods of measurement that can be used to assess a variety of individual characteristics that underlie personal decision making ([Society for Industrial and Organizational Psychology \(SIOP\), 2003](#)).

Selection test is any instrument used to make a decision about a potential employee best suited for a particular position and for the organization ([Gusdorf, 2008](#)). Using a variety of testing methods, applicants are rated on aptitude, personality, abilities, honesty and motivation and it is also thought that properly designed selection test are standardized, reliable, and valid in predicting an applicant's success on the job ([Gusdorf, 2008](#)). Another similar approach to drawing up an employee profile is to use the seven headings namely, education qualification/training, work experiences, skills and knowledge, physical attributes, personality/disposition, communication skills, and personal circumstances ([Failte Ireland \(FI\), 2013](#)).

To assess the job applicant, many of the firms were considered the assessment tests like test of general cognitive ability, work sample test, structured interviews, job knowledge tests, accomplishment record, integrity/honesty tests, unstructured interviews, bio-data measures, conscientiousness tests, reference checking, years of job experience, training and experience point method, years of education and interest ([Schmidt and Hunter, 1998](#)). Some organizations have opted for the employees not only focusing on work activities, traits and talents necessary to perform the job, but also but also spotlighting on worker requirements (Basic Skills, knowledge, education), worker characteristics (abilities, values, interests), occupational characteristics (labor market information), occupation-specific requirements (tasks, duties, occupational knowledge), and occupational requirements (work context, organizational context) ([USDLETA \(U.S. Department of Labor Employment and Training Administration\), 2000](#)).

One of the typical social competence test 'emotional intelligence test' involving the ability to monitor job incumbent emotions what categorized as self-awareness, managing emotions, motivating oneself, empathy and handling relationships ([Salovey and Mayer, 1990](#)). when employees want to measure abilities, skills, work styles, work values or vocational interests to predict job performance and managerial potential, they can do that by level of standardization, objectivity and quantifiability ([USDLETA \(U.S. Department of Labor Employment and Training Administration\), 2000](#)). [Shippman et al. \(2000\)](#) suggested competency based assessment, a whole-person approach for an individual, is a measure of knowledge, skills, abilities, behaviors, and other characteristics as a predictor of performance of work roles.

To hire the right person is the most crucial decision for management means to, the right individual manages himself with the organization and tasks, but the wrong one wastes both money and time ([Billikopf, 2014](#)). Knowledge in the particular field level is considered to be most important attribute that employers sought from a candidate. In another study, the common tools for assessment were ability test, achievement/proficiency test, bio-data inventories, employment interviews, personality inventories, honesty/integrity measures, education and experience requirements, recommendations and reference checks, assessment centers, medical examinations, and drug and alcohol tests ([USDLETA \(U.S. Department of Labor Employment and Training Administration\), 2000](#)).

In selecting an employee, the employers used some test that measures specific skills, knowledge and abilities whereas intelligence, personality and honesty are worth considerable ([Billikopf, 2014](#)). [Martin and Chapman \(2006\)](#) identified factors related to employment of graduates where 4 categories were considered, namely, (i) Work related skills i.e., work experience, work in team, leadership, professional commitment, knowledge of company, networking, IT skills, knowledge in their field of study; (ii) education i.e., grades in schools/colleges/universities; (iii) Interpersonal and Communication skills and personality traits i.e., motivation, self confidence, honesty, enthusiasms, initiatives, adaptability, extroversion; (iv) Experiences i.e. work experience and internship training. [Cunningham and Rowley \(2007\)](#) added the cultural influences with above those factors. But [Peppas and Yu \(2005\)](#) found discrepancy in US employers and Chinese employers for preferring enthusiasm and motivation respectively.

4. Methodology

The study is descriptive in nature conducted by using a survey method. The population was the population was the managers participated in the recruitment process and officers working at different organizations at entry level as such Dutch Bangla Bank, Bangladesh Shipping (Pvt.) Limited, Shahjalal Islami Bank; Ispahani Group (Tea Division) and Bangladesh Shipping Corporation (BSC) variables have been collected through a questionnaire. Structured questionnaire was used as a means of data collection and was collected via personally administered questionnaire. The questionnaire was distributed to the respondents based on considering representatives by personal judgment. In total 90, i.e., 20 managers and 70 officers were randomly selected from the sample organizations where response rate was 60%. The instrument was made up of sections of questions as per the factors in prearranged order. All items were measured on a five-point Likert Scale ranging from 1 'Strongly Disagree' to 5 'Strongly Agree'. Data

regarding the variables have been collected through a questionnaire. The collected data then were analyzed by applying factor analysis using SPSS 17.0.

5. Analysis

5.1. Factors to be Considered In Selecting an Employee for an Organization:

In the light of these findings, we were interested to know from our industry people the expectation of the graduate profile for recruitment of HR in their organizations. The data, thus, collected have been examined by factor analysis.

5.2. Principal Component Analysis

The variables have been further subjected to principal component analysis along with Varimax Rotation where by examination has got retention of nine factors. These factors have accumulated for 19.040%, 17.057%, 16.336%, 8.450%, 6.766%, 6.076%, 5.64%, 5.005%, & 4.612 of variation. This implies that the total variance accumulated for by all ten factors is more than 89% and remaining variance is explained by other factors.

5.3. Factor Analysis

The rotated factor matrix has been shown in [Table- 2](#). This shows that variables understudy have constituted ten groups/factors. It can be mentioned that the variable with factor loading of 0.50 and above has been considered for inclusion into the factors. These have been discussed in the following paragraphs.

5.3.1. Factor-I: Leadership Skill

Factor-I explains 19.040% of the total variations existing in the variable set. This factor has significant factor loadings on these variables which have formed this major cluster. This factor belongs to skills for selecting graduates such as leadership, oral communication, presentation skill, decision making capacity, capability to work in group, knowledge about corporate world, written communication, analytical ability, innovativeness, fellow feeling, and dedication to work. So, this factor provides a basis for conceptualization of a dimension, which may be identified as 'Leadership Skill Factor'.

5.3.2. Factor-Ii: Capacity Building

Factor-II explains 17.057% of the total variations existing in the variable set. This factor has significant factor loadings on these variables which have formed second important cluster. This factor is concerned with value and attitudes: other, general skill: other, critical thinking, technical skill: other, risk taking capacity for selecting employee at entry level, So, this factor provides a basis for conceptualization of a dimension, which may be identified as 'Capacity Building *Factor*'.

5.3.3. Factor-Iii: Belongingness

Factor-III explains 16.336% of the total variations existing in the variable set. This factor has significant factor loadings on these variables which have formed third cluster. This factor is concerned with value and attitudes: honesty, sacrificing tendency, belongingness, general skill: oral communication, technical skill: stress taking capability for selecting employee at entry level. So, this factor provides a basis for conceptualization of a dimension which may be identified as 'Belongingness Factor'.

5.3.4. Factor-Iv: It Skill

Factor-IV explains 8.450% of the total variations existing in the variable set. This factor has significant factor loadings on these variables which have formed fourth cluster. This factor belongs to skills for selecting graduates such as IT skill, net working capability, academic soundness in relevant area, time management capability, and appearance consciousness. So, this factor provides a basis for conceptualization of a dimension, which may be identified as 'IT Skill Factor'.

5.3.5. Factor-V: Personality

Factor-V: explains 6.766% of the total variations existing in the variable set. This factor has significant factor loadings on these variables which have formed fifth cluster. This factor is related to general skill: personality traits, personality inventories, and presence of wit for selecting graduate as an employee. So, this factor provides a basis for conceptualization of a dimension which may be identified as 'Personality *Factor*'.

5.3.6. Factor-Vi: Analytical Skill

Factor-VI explains 6.076% of the total variations existing in the variable set. This factor has significant factor loadings on these variables which have formed sixth cluster. This factor is related to commitment and diagnostic ability for selecting an employee. So, this factor provides a basis for conceptualization of a dimension which may be identified as 'Analytical Skill *Factor*'.

5.3.7. Factor-Vii: Human Skill

Factor-VII explains 5.64% of the total variations existing in the variable set. This factor has significant factor loadings on these variables which have formed seventh cluster. This factor is related to initiatives, value and attitudes: enthusiasm toward work, and obligation for selecting entry level employee. So, this factor provides a basis for conceptualization of a dimension which may be identified as 'Human Skill Factor'.

5.3.8. Factor-Viii: Change Management

Factor-VIII explains 5.005% of the total variations existing in the variable set. This factor has significant factor loadings on these variables which have formed eighth cluster. This factor is related to adaptability to change, and punctuality. So, this factor provides a basis for conceptualization of a dimension which may be identified as 'Change Management Factor'.

5.3.10. Factor-IX: Team Sprit

Factor-IX explains 4.612% of the total variations existing in the variable set. This factor has significant factor loadings on these variables which have formed ninth cluster. This factor is related to extroversion, cooperativeness, agreeableness, and empathy & handling relationship for entry level employee. So, this factor provides a basis for conceptualization of a dimension which may be identified as 'Team Sprit Factor'.

Table-1. Rankings of the influencing factors

S/N.	Factor	Average Score	Rank
I	<i>Leadership Skill</i>	4.09	5
II	<i>Capacity Building</i>	2.21	8
III	<i>Belongingness</i>	3.35	2
IV	<i>IT Skill</i>	2.38	7
V	<i>Personality</i>	2.11	9
VI	<i>Analytical Skill</i>	3.16	3
VII	<i>Human Skill</i>	2.99	6
VIII	<i>Change Management</i>	3.09	4
IX	<i>Team Sprit</i>	3.56	1

Note: Data have been compiled by the researcher

The ranking shows that factor I: *Leadership Skill* Factor is the most important factor. This factor is related to leadership, oral communication, presentation skill, decision making capacity, capability to work in group, knowledge about corporate world, written communication, analytical ability, innovativeness, fellow feeling, and dedication to work. The second most important factor is the IX: *Team Sprit* Factor. This factor is concerned with extroversion, cooperativeness, agreeableness, and empathy & handling relationship for entry level employee.

6. Conclusion

In selecting an employee for an organization is a typical work employers do in practical field. In view of experiences of employers and requirements of the job, different skills supposed to be highlighted during selection. The skills employers considered are not bound to rigidity among the factors, but situation and scenario might influence the selection process undoubtedly. However, it will not always be an option to recruit or promote an employee from within. The important message is not to overlook a potential applicant already working for as it can have a detrimental effect on their morale and their commitment to the organization.

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Table-2. Rotated Component Matrix(a)

	Component								
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Leadership Skill	0.946	0.012	0.033	0.075	-0.1	0.096	0.09	0.051	0.221
Oral Communication Skill	0.872	0.276	0.291	0.059	0.129	0	0.14	-0.007	0.019
Presentation Skill	0.842	0.424	0.217	0.033	0.037	-0.062	0.166	0.066	0.052
Decision making Capacity	0.785	0.151	0.395	-0.001	0.138	0.137	0.255	0.095	-0.144
Capability to work in group	0.743	0.481	0.339	0.084	0.013	-0.127	-0.085	0.138	0.018
knowledge about Corporate World	0.705	-0.208	0.473	0.19	0.311	0.219	-0.095	-0.105	-0.051
Written Communication Skill	0.689	-0.348	0.255	0.053	0.041	0.145	0.154	0.141	0.471
Analytical Ability	0.677	0.203	0.261	0.4	0.212	0.202	0.201	0.147	-0.222
Innovativeness	0.669	-0.064	-0.258	0.077	0.362	0.276	-0.463	0.104	-0.111
Fellow Feeling	0.66	0.208	0.444	0.069	0.11	-0.122	0.151	0.373	0.186
Dedication to work	0.645	0.406	-0.223	-0.008	-0.37	-0.239	-0.024	0.276	0.061
Value and Attitude: Other	-0.004	0.853	0.025	-0.293	-0.086	0.169	-0.066	0.012	-0.166
General Skill: Other	0.034	0.832	0.329	0.218	0.101	-0.149	0.064	0.078	0.017
Critical Thinking	0.257	0.778	-0.248	0.074	-0.176	0.237	0.286	0.192	0.074
Technical Skill: Other	0.121	0.761	-0.314	0.027	-0.029	0.008	0.05	0.303	-0.017
Risk taking Capacity	0.01	0.745	-0.165	0.138	-0.179	-0.236	0.263	0.446	0.041
Value and Attitude: Honesty	0.115	0.021	0.833	0.146	0.332	-0.009	0.271	-0.009	-0.032
Sacrificing Tendency	0.274	0.195	0.832	-0.102	0.226	-0.074	0.206	-0.203	-0.003
Belongingness	0.031	-0.021	0.825	-0.048	-0.121	-0.163	-0.199	0.267	-0.199
General Skill: Oral Communication	0.07	0.422	0.824	-0.036	0.116	-0.005	0.149	0.05	0.178
Technical Skill: Stress taking Capacity	0.335	0.075	0.773	0.263	-0.201	-0.284	0.066	0.02	-0.213
IT Skill	0.031	-0.112	0.065	0.873	0.101	0.226	-0.166	0.234	-0.192
Networking Capacity	-0.099	0.337	-0.156	0.743	0.129	0.041	0.285	-0.057	0.121
Academic Soundness in relevant area	0.224	-0.155	0.246	0.714	0.157	0.135	-0.094	-0.022	0.366
Time Management Capability	0.196	0.496	0.119	0.5	0.478	-0.118	0.23	-0.009	0.155
Appearance Consciousness	0.441	0.164	-0.442	0.478	0.26	0.106	0.144	0.399	-0.075
Personality Inventories	0.221	0.356	0.161	0.104	0.739	0.236	0.117	0.113	0.059
Presence of wit	0.353	0.473	0.014	-0.168	0.627	-0.222	0.29	-0.14	-0.156
Personality Traits	0.13	0.315	-0.26	0.308	0.622	0.367	-0.094	0.272	-0.118
Commitment	0.046	-0.111	-0.136	0.169	-0.142	0.892	0.073	0.039	-0.045
Diagnostic Skill	0.107	0.189	-0.145	0.176	0.202	0.852	-0.285	0.062	-0.06
Initiatives	0.495	0.277	0.06	0.217	0.139	-0.028	0.637	0.205	-0.175
Value and Attitude: Enthusiasm toward work	0.282	0.308	0.499	-0.093	0.162	-0.236	0.546	0.027	-0.118
Obligation	0.344	0.084	0.41	0.533	-0.175	-0.04	0.535	-0.059	-0.142
Adaptability to change	0.22	0.296	0.069	0.222	0.318	0.046	-0.016	0.7	0.106
Punctuality	0.637	0.043	0.172	-0.129	-0.065	0.035	0.001	0.67	-0.25
Cooperativeness	-0.132	-0.255	-0.099	-0.115	-0.049	-0.145	-0.056	-0.392	0.629
Extroversion	0.069	0.007	-0.016	0.054	-0.139	-0.118	-0.124	0.021	0.959
Agreeableness	0.27	0.532	-0.003	0.064	-0.135	0.099	0.369	0.12	0.497
Empathy and Handling Relationship	0.52	-0.14	0.375	-0.098	-0.072	0.397	0.103	0.09	0.606

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis. **Rotation Method:** Varimax with Kaiser Normalization. **a** Rotation converged in 21 iterations.

Table-3. Total Variance Explained

Component	Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	19.586	36.955	36.955	10.091	19.040	19.040
2	7.459	14.073	51.028	9.040	17.057	36.097
3	4.928	9.298	60.327	8.658	16.336	52.433
4	4.055	7.651	67.978	4.478	8.450	60.883
5	3.530	6.661	74.639	3.586	6.766	67.649
6	2.373	4.477	79.116	3.220	6.076	73.725
7	2.052	3.872	82.988	3.007	5.674	79.399
8	1.683	3.175	86.163	2.653	5.005	84.404
9	1.513	2.854	89.017	2.445	4.612	89.017

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Table-4. Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation
Leadership Skill	3.9	.301
Oral Communication Skill	3.95	.218
Presentation Skill	3.71	.561
Decision making Capacity	3.81	.402
Capability to work in group	3.67	.577
Knowledge about Corporate World	3.38	.669
Written Communication Skill	3.52	.602
Analytical Ability	4.62	.669
Innovativeness	4.71	.463
Fellow Feeling	4.81	.402
Dedication to work	4.86	.478
Value and Attitude: Other	2.16	.436
General Skill: Other	2.17	.598
Critical Thinking	2.43	.676
Technical Skill: Other	2.05	.740
Risk taking Capacity	2.24	.700
Value and Attitude: Honesty	3	.707
Sacrificing Tendency	3.43	.746
Belongingness	3.14	.854
General Skill: Oral Communication	3.48	.680
Technical Skill: Stress taking Capacity	3.71	.463
IT Skill	2.9	.301
Networking Capacity	2.11	.512
Academic Soundness in relevant area	2.43	.746
Time Management Capability	2.38	.805
Appearance Consciousness	2.07	.746
Personality Inventories	2.38	.805
Presence of wit	1.48	.814
Personality Traits	2.48	.602
Commitment	3.18	.680
Diagnostic Skill	3.14	.995
Initiatives	3.27	.676
Value and Attitude: Enthusiasm toward work	3.25	.676
Obligation	2.45	.218
Adaptability to change	3.1	.602
Punctuality	3.08	.805
Cooperativeness	3.1	.768
Extroversion	3.71	.561
Agreeableness	3.86	.359
Empathy and Handling Relationship	3.55	.949